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THE WAYS OF WORD-FORMATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. English is considered to be a worldwide language. Typically mostly due to the word formation instrument that's utilized to design modern words within the language within the to begin with put. The English language has ended up more versatile as a result of the expansive sum of lexicon accessible. This article describes about some ways of word-formation in English language,

Keywords: Word-formation, affixation, word-cluster, conversion, abbreviations.

The method of word formation is broadly recognised as a wonder that's natural to human life all around the world. As characterized by Trask, the method of word formation could be a strategy of making modern words from already existing components. In the interim, agreeing to Hacken and Thomas, the word creation prepare is the strategy through which modern words are made based on a set of rules. Aside from that, agreeing to Plag, the term "word formation process" alludes to the method of making unused words from existing ones. Based on the previous portrayal, it can be inferred that the word arrangement prepare is the strategy of building modern words from existing words in agreement with certain rules. The method of word arrangement can be both beneficial and non-productive. In etymology (especially morphology and lexicology), word formation alludes to the ways in which modern words are shaped on the premise of other words or morphemes. This is often too known as derivational morphology. Word formation can indicate either a state or a handle, and it can be seen either diachronically (through diverse periods in history) or synchronically (at one specific period in time). Word-formation is the process of creating new words from the material available in the language after certain structural and semantic formulas and patterns. For instance, the noun driver is formed after the pattern v+er, i. e. a verb-stem+the noun-forming suffix -er. The meaning of the noun driver is related to the meanings of the stem drive and the suffix -er. [1.135]

Word-formation is the creation of new words from the elements existing in the language. Every language has its own structural patterns of word-formation. Words like “writer”, “worker”, “teacher”, “manager” and many others follow the structural pattern of word-formation. In addition, in English language we can meet a lot of definitions about word-formation in different author’s books.

Word-formation is that branch of the science of language which the patterns on which language forms new lexical units, i. e. words [2.108]

The term “word-formation” is applied to the process by which new words are formed by adding prefixes and suffixes or both to a root-form already in existence [J.A.Sheard] By word-formation on a foreign basis of coining we understand derivation on the morphologic basis of another language. In English most learned, scientific or technical words are formed on the morphologic basis of Latin and Greek [6.26]

Affixation – is the formation of words with the help of derivational affixes. Words which consist of a root and an affix (or several affixes) are called derived words or derivatives and are produced by the process of word building known as affixation.[6.28].

Affixation is subdivided into prefixation and suffixation. Derivational morphemes added before the stem of a word are called prefixes (Ex. un+like) and the derivational morphemes added after the stem of the word are called suffixes (hand+ful). [3.30]

Word cluster – is a group of words which have semantically and phonetically correlated with identical root morphemes. Ex. to lead, leader, leadership etc. The members of a word cluster belong as a rule to different parts of speech and are joined together only by the identity of the root morpheme. [3.42]

Conversion – is a very productive way of forming new words in modern English, for example, work (n) – to work (v), pen (n) – to pen (v), walk (n) – to walk (v). The term “Conversion” was first used by Sweet in his book “New English Grammar” in 1892. [6.39]

Word-formation in English presents a major interest in the extensive development of the so-called conversion or zero-derivation. Conversion is known to have existed at all stages of the development of the language. The facility of converting a noun into a verb mother–to mother, an adjective into a noun my native town–a native of the town, a verb into a noun to say–a say, etc., without any distinct ending, in fact, the most striking feature of modern English

organically related to the functioning of its structural elements at different levels. [7.83]

Word composition – modern English is very rich in compound words. Compound words are made up by joining two or more stems. For instance, taxi-driver, paint-box, bookcase. A compound word has a single semantic structure. We distinguish the meaning of the compound words from the combined lexical meanings of its components. Ex. “pencil-case” – is a case for pencils. The meaning of the compound words is derived not only from the combined lexical meanings of its components but also from the order and arrangement of the stem. A change in the order of components of compound words brings a change in their lexical meaning. [3.54]

Word-compounding is a process of similar to but not the same as telescoping or blends; two words are joined, but compounding differs in that no part of either word is lost, ex. blackbird, bookcase in the examples the elements have been fused, making one word. [I.K.Sheard] Compound words are words consisting of at least two stems which occur in the language as free forms. In a compound word the immediate constituents obtain integrity and structural cohesion that make them function in a sentence as a separate lexical unit. [4.108]

Word-composition or compounding is a distinct type of words made up by joining together two stems (mostly stems of notional parts of speech). (Ginzburg R.S. and others) [3.58]

Abbreviations – consist of the first letters of a word group or a compound word (USA, BBC, NATO) or the component of a two member word group H (hydrogin) –bomb, V.–Day (Victory Day) is shortened. The last one is not changed.

Clipping – consists in the cutting off one or several syllables of a word. In many cases the stressed syllables are preserved. Ex. Sis.(sister), Jap.(Japanese), doc.(doctor), phone.(telephone), lab.(laboratory).

Clipping is classified into the following types depending on which part of the word is clipped:

- 1) Words that have been shortened at the end: ex. ad (advertisement), lab (laboratory), vac (vacuum cleaner);
- 2) Words that have been shortened at the beginning: ex. car (motor-car), phone (telephone), van (caravan), cast (broadcast);
- 3) Words in which syllables have been omitted from the middle called syncope: ex. maths (mathematics), specs (spectacles);

4) Words that have been shortened at the beginning and at the end: ex. flu (influenza), tec (detective), frig (refrigerator).

Clippings do not always coincide in meaning with the original word. Ex. doc and doctor have the meaning one who practices medicine, but doctor is also the highest degree given by a university to a scholar or scientist and a person who has received such a degree whereas doc is not used with these meanings.

Sound interchange – is an alternation in the phonetic composition of the root. Ex. food (n) – feed (v), speak (v) – speech (n), strong (adj) – strength (n). Soundinterchange may be divided into vowel interchange and consonant interchange. Ex. full- to fill, food- to feed, advice-to advice, use-to use.

Back-formation – The term “back-formation” has diachronic relevance (historical meaning). Ex. the nouns beggar, butler, cobbler, typewriter are very much like the nouns actor, painter, teacher which have the suffixes –er, -or. On the analogy of the derivatives teacher, speaker, reader the words beggar, butler, cobbler, typewriter etc. synchronically are derived from to beg, to butle, to cob, to typewrite because we do not feel any difference between the relationship “speak-speaker” and “beg-beggar”. But if we study their origin we see butle was derived from “butler”, “to beg” was derived from “beggar” (begar comes from French “begard”, “begart”). So backformation denotes the derivation of new words by subtracting a real or supposed affix from existing words through misinterpretation of their structure.

Blending – is the formation of a new word by a connection of parts of two words to form one word. Ex. the noun “smog” is composed of the parts of nouns “smoke” and “fog” sm (oke+f) og=smog. The result of blending is an unanalysable simple word. We do not analyse the blended words (sm+og) because their parts can’t be called morphemes. [3.62]

Blends are also words formed from a word-group or two synonyms. In blends two ways of word-building are combined: abbreviation and composition. To form a blend we clip the end of the first component (apocope) and the beginning of the second component (apheresis). As a result we have a compound shortened word. One of the first blends in English was the word “smog” from two synonyms: smoke and fog which means smoke mixed with fog. From the component the beginning is taken from the second one the end “o” is common for both of them.

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